

PERIÓDICO TCHÊ QUÍMICA ANNUAL TRANSPARENCY REPORT

Ketevan Kupatadze¹, Shaima Rabeea Banoon², Luis Alcides Brandini De Boni³

¹ Periódico Tchê Química, Editor in Chief. Full professor at Ilia State University, Faculty of Natural Science and Medicine, Tbilisi, Georgia.

² Periódico Tchê Química, Editor in Chief. Department of Biology, College of Science, University of Misan, Maysan, Iraq.

³ Periódico Tchê Química, Managing Editor, Brazil.

* *Correspondence author*
email: tchequimica@tchequimica.com

Accepted 25 November 2024

In **2023**, the Periódico Tchê Química introduced the practice of producing an annual transparency report to give authors and institutions access to useful information about the journal. The main facts were presented in bullet points to make the report succinct. In **2024**, we are continuing this practice.

- **Current Editor-in-Cheife:** Dr. Ketevan Kupatadze, Ilia State University, Georgia; MsC. Shaima Rabeea Banoon, Misan University, Iraq.
- **Currently Edited by:** Araucaria Associação Científica (CNPJ # 52.968.321/0001-88).
- **Number of countries represented in the journal council:** 8.
- **Number of conferences the journal was invited to publish the resulting material:** 2.
- **Number of conferences that the journal is publishing the resulting materials:** 2.
- **Number of manuscripts received in 2024:** 102
- **Number of manuscripts published in 2024:** 17
- **Amount of manuscripts that will continue the publication process in 2025:** around 40
- **Amount of improper submissions:** 20
- **Amount of rectified submissions:** 26
- **Amount of retractions:** 11
- **Financial support received from other institutions (in USD):** \$ 0,00. A proudly independent journal.
- **Indexed in:** WoS, Index Copernicus, Latindex, and I2OR.
- **Publication fees:** All authors have published in 2024 without any charges from the journal side. All journal downloads are also freely available on the journal website. This means that the Araucaria Scientific Association has absorbed all publication costs in 2024.